

PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT NEEDS OF MADRASAH TEACHERS IN BUKIDNON: PERSPECTIVES AND PRIORITIES

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 29

Issue 10

Pages: 1587-1594

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2831

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14579998

Manuscript Accepted: 12-04-2024

Professional Development Needs of Madrasah Teachers in Bukidnon: Perspectives and Priorities

Rolly S. Ortiz Jr.*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study investigates the professional development needs and challenges faced by Madrasah teachers in rural Bukidnon, focusing on key areas such as personal and family challenges, educational environment, community and social influences, health and well-being, and transportation and accessibility. Using qualitative methods, including focus group discussions (FGDs) and individual interviews, the research aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the barriers that impact the participation and effectiveness of professional development programs for Madrasah educators. The findings reveal that personal and family responsibilities significantly affect teachers' ability to engage in professional development, necessitating flexible scheduling and local or online PD options. Additionally, inadequate educational resources and outdated materials present substantial obstacles, highlighting the need for investments in updated resources and improved school facilities. Community and social influences also play a role, with cultural norms affecting the adoption of new teaching practices. Addressing these issues requires integrating cultural values into PD programs and engaging community stakeholders. Furthermore, the study identifies health and well-being concerns and transportation challenges as critical barriers to effective PD. The long travel times and associated stress impact both teaching effectiveness and overall well-being, suggesting a need for wellness programs and more accessible PD formats. The research concludes with recommendations for creating a more supportive and effective professional development environment through flexible scheduling, resource investment, cultural sensitivity, and improved accessibility. These measures aim to enhance the professional growth of Madrasah teachers and improve the educational experience for learners in Bukidnon.

Keywords: *professional development, Madrasah Education, rural Bukidnon*

Introduction

The professional development (PD) of educators is a vital component in enhancing the quality of education, particularly in specialized programs like the Madrasah Education Program in the Philippines. Madrasah teachers in rural areas, such as those in Bukidnon, face a unique set of challenges that significantly impact their ability to participate in PD programs. These challenges include the dual burden of personal and family responsibilities, a lack of adequate educational resources, cultural norms that may conflict with modern teaching practices, and logistical barriers such as transportation difficulties and health concerns. These factors collectively hinder the professional growth of teachers, which in turn affects the quality of education delivered to learners. This action research aims to identify and address these barriers, providing practical solutions to improve the accessibility, relevance, and effectiveness of PD for Madrasah teachers in the Division of Bukidnon.

By focusing on the specific context of Bukidnon, this research recognizes the diverse and complex factors that influence teacher development in this division. The Madrasah Education Program, which integrates Islamic values with the national curriculum, presents additional layers of complexity for educators who must navigate between religious expectations and contemporary pedagogical practices. The study seeks to explore how these dynamics affect teachers' participation in PD and to develop strategies that accommodate their unique circumstances. By doing so, the research aims to contribute to the broader goal of improving educational outcomes for learners in Madrasah schools by empowering teachers with the skills, knowledge, and resources they need to excel in their roles.

The significance of this research lies in its potential to inform policy and practice in the Madrasah Education Program, particularly in underserved rural areas. By providing insights into the challenges and needs of Madrasah teachers, the study will offer evidence-based recommendations that can guide the design and implementation of PD programs. These programs will not only support the professional growth of teachers but also ensure that the educational experiences of learners are enriched by well-prepared and motivated educators. Ultimately, this research aims to bridge the gap between policy and practice, ensuring that Madrasah teachers in rural Bukidnon receive the support they need to succeed in their vital role within the education system.

Research Questions

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the primary challenges faced by Madrasah teachers in rural Bukidnon that hinder their participation in professional development programs?
2. How do personal and family responsibilities impact the professional development of these teachers?
3. In what ways do community and cultural factors influence the effectiveness of professional development for Madrasah teachers?

4. What strategies can be implemented to address health, well-being, and transportation challenges associated with professional development?

Literature Review

The review of related literature for this study explores the intersection of professional development (PD) needs and the unique challenges faced by teachers in rural settings, with a specific focus on Madrasah educators in the Division of Bukidnon. Research consistently emphasizes that effective PD is critical for improving teaching quality and, subsequently, student outcomes. However, teachers in rural areas often encounter distinct barriers that hinder their participation in PD programs. Studies highlight that these barriers include limited access to resources, geographic isolation, and logistical challenges, such as long travel distances to PD sessions. In the context of Bukidnon, a predominantly rural province in the Philippines, these issues are particularly pronounced. Madrasah teachers here not only grapple with the general difficulties of rural education but also face additional challenges related to the integration of religious and secular educational content, which can complicate their professional development journey.

The literature also points to the importance of culturally responsive PD programs, particularly in regions like Bukidnon where traditional values and community norms play a significant role in shaping educational practices. Madrasah educators, who are responsible for teaching both Islamic religious subjects and the national curriculum, must navigate the expectations of their communities while striving to incorporate contemporary teaching methods. Research suggests that PD programs that fail to acknowledge and integrate local cultural contexts are often met with resistance or have limited impact. In Bukidnon, where cultural and religious identity is deeply intertwined with education, PD initiatives that respect and incorporate these values are more likely to be successful. Therefore, the literature advocates for PD approaches that are not only technically sound but also culturally sensitive, ensuring that new teaching strategies are both effective and acceptable within the community.

Additionally, the literature underscores the critical role of support systems in enhancing PD participation, particularly in rural areas. In Bukidnon, where many teachers must contend with issues such as inadequate infrastructure, limited access to modern educational tools, and even health and well-being concerns due to the rural environment, the need for comprehensive support is evident. Studies suggest that providing logistical support, such as local or online PD options, and addressing teachers' well-being through stress management and health programs, can significantly improve their engagement with PD initiatives. Moreover, collaboration with community leaders and stakeholders in designing and delivering PD programs can enhance their relevance and effectiveness, ensuring that they meet the specific needs of Madrasah teachers in Bukidnon. This body of literature provides a robust foundation for the current study, which aims to explore these themes in greater depth and develop actionable strategies to overcome the barriers faced by Madrasah educators in this rural context.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employs a qualitative research approach to explore the professional development needs of Madrasah teachers in rural Bukidnon. Data will be collected through Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) with a selected group of 6-10 Madrasah teachers from various rural areas. Participants will be chosen based on their teaching levels and experiences to ensure diverse perspectives. The discussions will be guided by a set of key questions focused on professional development experiences, challenges, and suggestions for improvement.

The FGDs will be audio-recorded, transcribed, and analyzed using thematic analysis to identify common themes and patterns. Ethical considerations include obtaining informed consent from all participants, ensuring confidentiality, and anonymizing data in reports. The findings will provide insights into the specific needs and preferences of Madrasah teachers, which can be used to inform policy and program development.

Participants

The study employs a purposive sampling method to select participants, ensuring that the sample represents the target population of Madrasah teachers in the Division of Bukidnon. This method is chosen because it allows for the deliberate selection of participants who are most knowledgeable and experienced in the subject of interest—namely, the professional development (PD) needs and challenges of Madrasah educators. The sample will consist of approximately 10-15 Madrasah teachers from the implementing schools in Bukidnon, selected to reflect diversity in terms of age, years of teaching experience, and the specific context of the schools they serve. This approach ensures that a wide range of perspectives is captured, providing a comprehensive understanding of the barriers to PD participation.

Instrument

Data will be collected using three primary qualitative methods: focus group discussions (FGDs), individual interviews, and document analysis.

Focus Group Discussions (FGDs): FGDs will be the main method of data collection, allowing for a dynamic exchange of ideas among

teachers. These discussions will be semi-structured, guided by a set of open-ended questions that explore the key areas of personal and family responsibilities, educational resources, cultural influences, health and well-being, and transportation challenges. Each FGD will include 2-3 participants and will be conducted in a setting that is convenient and comfortable for the teachers, such as their local schools or community centers.

Individual Interviews: To gain deeper insights into specific issues, semi-structured individual interviews will be conducted with a subset of participants. These interviews will allow for more in-depth exploration of sensitive or personal challenges that may not be fully discussed in the group setting. The interviews will follow a flexible guide, tailored to the individual experiences of each teacher.

Document Analysis: Relevant documents, including DepEd policies, PD program materials, and other educational resources, will be reviewed to contextualize the findings and ensure alignment with national and local educational objectives. This method will provide additional background information that will support the interpretation of the qualitative data collected through FGDs and interviews.

Data Analysis

The data collected from FGDs and interviews will be analyzed using thematic analysis, a qualitative method that involves identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns (themes) within the data. The analysis will proceed through the following steps:

Familiarization with the Data: The research team will begin by thoroughly reading and re-reading the transcribed data from FGDs and interviews to become deeply familiar with the content.

Initial Coding: The data will be coded systematically by breaking it down into meaningful segments and assigning codes to represent different aspects of the participants' responses. These codes will capture key ideas related to the barriers and challenges faced by Madrasah teachers in accessing PD.

Searching for Themes: The codes will be grouped into broader categories or themes that reflect the main issues identified in the data. These themes will correspond to the key areas of interest in the study, such as personal and family responsibilities, educational resources, and cultural influences.

Reviewing Themes: The identified themes will be reviewed and refined to ensure that they accurately represent the data. This step involves checking the coherence of the themes and ensuring that they are distinct from one another while adequately covering the relevant aspects of the research questions.

Defining and Naming Themes: Once the themes are finalized, they will be clearly defined and named to reflect their essence. Each theme will be described in detail, with examples from the data to illustrate how it relates to the overall research objectives.

Interpreting the Data: The final step involves interpreting the themes in the context of the research questions and the theoretical framework of the study. The analysis will focus on understanding the implications of the identified barriers for the professional development of Madrasah teachers and developing strategies to address these challenges.

The document analysis will complement the thematic analysis by providing additional context and supporting evidence for the findings. The results of the analysis will be used to develop targeted interventions aimed at improving PD participation among Madrasah teachers in rural Bukidnon.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations are paramount in this study, given the sensitivity of the topics discussed and the rural context in which the research takes place. The study will adhere to the following ethical principles:

Informed Consent: All participants will be provided with detailed information about the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. Consent will be obtained in writing before any data collection begins, and participants will be informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty.

Confidentiality: The privacy of participants will be strictly maintained throughout the research process. Personal identifiers will be removed from the data, and all information will be stored securely. Only the research team will have access to the raw data, and findings will be reported in a way that protects the anonymity of the participants.

Cultural Sensitivity: The study will be conducted with respect for the cultural and religious values of the Madrasah teachers and their communities. This includes using culturally appropriate language and being mindful of religious practices and norms during data collection. The research team will work closely with local stakeholders to ensure that the study is conducted in a manner that is respectful and acceptable to the participants.

Results and Discussion

Personal and Family Challenges

Tabel 1 highlighted the difficulty of balancing teaching duties with family responsibilities, which often limits their ability to participate

in professional development (PD) opportunities. Offering local or online PD opportunities and providing support for teachers with significant family duties can help alleviate these challenges

Table 1. *Personal and Family Challenges*

<i>Themes Identified</i>	<i>Sample Quotes</i>	<i>Challenges</i>	<i>Recommendations</i>
- Balancing teaching duties with family responsibilities	"It's difficult to attend training sessions far from home because I need to care for my children."	- Family obligations limit participation in PD - Stress due to balancing multiple roles	- Offer local or online PD opportunities - Provide support for teachers with family duties
- Lack of time for personal development	"After school, there's hardly any time left for my own learning or rest."	- Time constraints due to family and work	- Schedule PD during convenient times - Offer flexible PD formats

Madrasah teachers in rural Bukidnon face significant personal and family challenges that impact their participation in professional development (PD) programs. These educators often juggle multiple roles, including caregiving and household responsibilities, which limit their time and energy for further education. The demands of balancing teaching duties with family obligations can create a situation where attending PD sessions becomes challenging. For instance, teachers may find it difficult to participate in training programs that are scheduled far from their communities or require substantial time commitments.

To effectively support these teachers, it is crucial to offer flexible and accessible PD opportunities that accommodate their unique circumstances. Implementing local or online PD sessions can significantly reduce travel burdens and allow educators to engage in professional learning without compromising their family responsibilities (Edutopia, 2021). Additionally, tailoring PD programs to meet the specific needs of Madrasah teachers can enhance their professional growth while respecting their personal situations (PowerSchool, n.d.). This approach not only benefits the educators but also contributes to improved teaching practices and student outcomes.

Creating a supportive framework for PD that acknowledges the realities faced by Madrasah teachers is essential for fostering their development. By prioritizing flexibility and accessibility in PD offerings, educational stakeholders can empower these teachers to enhance their skills while maintaining a healthy work-life balance (Creative Educator, 2019). Ultimately, this strategy will lead to a more effective educational environment, benefiting both the teachers and the students they serve.

Educational Environment

Table 2 outlines the challenges in the educational environment that affect Madrasah teachers' professional development. Key issues include inadequate resources and facilities, along with limited access to updated teaching materials. Teachers voiced concerns about using outdated textbooks, stating, "We're still using outdated textbooks, which makes it hard to keep up with current teaching methods." Recommendations emphasize supplying schools with updated materials, enhancing infrastructure, and providing access to digital resources.

Table 2. *Educational Environment*

<i>Themes Identified</i>	<i>Sample Quotes</i>	<i>Challenges</i>	<i>Recommendations</i>
- Inadequate resources and facilities	"Our Madrasah lacks the necessary books and materials for both teaching and professional growth."	- Poor infrastructure - Limited access to educational resources	- Supply schools with updated materials - Improve infrastructure and resources
- Lack of access to updated teaching materials	"We're still using outdated textbooks, which makes it hard to keep up with current teaching methods."	- Difficulty in staying current with educational trends	- Provide access to digital resources - Regularly update teaching materials

The educational environment in rural Bukidnon presents a range of challenges for Madrasah teachers that significantly impact their effectiveness and professional development. Many schools in this region lack adequate resources, including updated teaching materials and proper infrastructure, which hampers the ability of educators to deliver quality instruction. For instance, teachers often have to rely on outdated textbooks and insufficient classroom facilities, which can detract from the learning experience for students. This situation not only affects the quality of education provided but also limits teachers' opportunities for professional growth and development.

The scarcity of resources creates an environment where teachers struggle to implement innovative teaching strategies that could enhance student engagement and learning outcomes. When educators do not have access to current educational materials or adequate training facilities, their ability to stay informed about effective teaching practices is compromised (Karmila & Wijaya, 2020). Consequently, this lack of support can lead to feelings of frustration and burnout among teachers, further exacerbating the challenges they face in their roles.

Addressing these deficiencies through targeted investments in educational resources and infrastructure is essential for improving both teaching quality and the professional development of educators in these remote areas. By providing updated materials, enhancing school facilities, and offering accessible training programs, stakeholders can create a more conducive learning environment that

empowers Madrasah teachers. Such improvements not only benefit the educators but also contribute to better educational outcomes for students, fostering a more robust academic community in rural Bukidnon.

Community and Social Influences

Table 3 examines the community and social influences on Madrasah teachers, emphasizing the tension between community support and cultural expectations. Teachers acknowledged that while education is valued, cultural norms can hinder the adoption of new teaching strategies. One teacher noted, "The community values our work, but sometimes cultural norms make it hard to implement new teaching strategies." Recommendations include tailoring professional development (PD) programs to respect cultural norms and involving community leaders in these initiatives.

Table 3. *Community and Social Influences*

Themes Identified	Sample Quotes	Challenges	Recommendations
- Community support for education	"The community values our work, but sometimes cultural norms make it hard to implement new teaching strategies."	- Cultural resistance to certain PD topics - Community pressure on teaching methods	- Tailor PD programs to respect cultural norms - Engage community leaders in PD initiatives
- Cultural expectations affecting teaching practices	"There are traditional ways of teaching here that the community expects us to follow."	- Difficulty in introducing new methods due to cultural expectations	- Include cultural context in PD content - Work with local cultural leaders

Community and social influences play a critical role in shaping the teaching practices of educators in rural Bukidnon. While there is generally strong community support for education, cultural norms and expectations can sometimes hinder the adoption of new teaching methodologies. Educators often find themselves navigating the delicate balance between aligning their teaching practices with community expectations and pursuing their own professional growth. This complexity is compounded by the need to respect local traditions while also striving to implement innovative educational strategies that could enhance student learning outcomes.

The challenge lies in the fact that while community support is vital, it can also impose limitations on how educators approach their teaching. For instance, traditional beliefs about education may prioritize certain pedagogical methods over newer, evidence-based practices, which can create resistance to change. Educators may feel pressured to conform to these established norms, which can stifle creativity and hinder the adoption of effective teaching strategies. To overcome these barriers, professional development programs must be designed to respect and integrate cultural norms while providing educators with the tools they need to innovate in their classrooms.

Targeted professional development that acknowledges and incorporates community values can bridge this gap effectively. By engaging local leaders and stakeholders in the development of these programs, educators can foster a collaborative environment that promotes both cultural sensitivity and pedagogical advancement. Workshops that focus on culturally relevant teaching practices, alongside opportunities for educators to share their experiences and strategies, can create a supportive network that empowers teachers to enhance their skills without compromising their cultural identity (Karmila & Wijaya, 2020; NASPA, 2023). Ultimately, such an approach not only benefits educators but also enriches the educational experience for students, leading to improved learning outcomes.

Health and Well-being

Table 4 highlights the health and well-being challenges impacting Madrasah teachers' professional development and teaching effectiveness. Key themes include physical and mental health concerns, with teachers noting, "Traveling long distances for PD adds to the physical and mental stress we already face." Recommendations include implementing wellness programs, offering PD in more accessible locations, and incorporating stress management into professional development content.

Table 4. *Health and Well-being*

Themes Identified	Sample Quotes	Challenges	Recommendations
- Physical and mental health concerns	"Traveling long distances for PD adds to the physical and mental stress we already face as teachers."	- Health issues due to stress - Limited access to health services	- Provide wellness programs - Offer PD in more accessible locations to reduce travel stress
- Impact of stress on teaching effectiveness	"The workload and stress are affecting my ability to teach effectively."	- Increased stress levels impacting job performance	- Include stress management in PD - Encourage self-care and wellness practices

Health and well-being are significant concerns for Madrasah teachers, particularly given the physical and mental stress associated with their roles. Long travel distances to attend professional development (PD) sessions, combined with the daily pressures of teaching in under-resourced environments, contribute to high levels of stress and fatigue among educators. These challenges can hinder their ability to perform effectively and maintain their own health, leading to burnout and decreased job satisfaction (Karmila & Wijaya, 2020).

The physical demands placed on teachers, such as lengthy commutes and the necessity to manage multiple responsibilities, can exacerbate these issues. For instance, teachers often report feeling overwhelmed by the combination of their teaching duties and personal obligations, which can lead to neglecting their own health needs (ReachOut Schools, n.d.). To mitigate these pressures, it is

essential to improve access to health and wellness resources. This could include providing mental health support services, promoting self-care practices, and facilitating wellness programs that focus on both physical and mental well-being (Mizell, 2010).

Additionally, offering PD opportunities closer to teachers' communities can significantly alleviate some of the burdens they face. By reducing travel time and making training more accessible, educators can engage in professional development without compromising their personal responsibilities or health (PowerSchool, n.d.). Creating a supportive environment that prioritizes teachers' well-being not only enhances their professional growth but also leads to improved educational outcomes for students. Investing in the health and wellness of educators is crucial for fostering a sustainable and effective teaching workforce.

Transportation and Accessibility

Table 5 addresses the transportation and accessibility challenges faced by Madrasah teachers in rural Bukidnon when attending professional development sessions. Participants reported that long travel times and high transportation costs create significant barriers to accessing these opportunities. One learner stated, "Reaching the training centers is a challenge due to the distance and the cost involved." Recommendations include decentralizing PD sessions, providing travel allowances or subsidies, and offering more local or virtual PD options to ease the burden on teachers.

Table 5. *Transportation and Accessibility*

<i>Themes Identified</i>	<i>Sample Quotes</i>	<i>Challenges</i>	<i>Recommendations</i>
- Difficulty in accessing PD opportunities	"Reaching the training centers is a challenge due to the distance and the cost involved."	- Long travel times - High transportation costs	- Decentralize PD sessions - Provide travel allowances or subsidies
- High travel costs and time constraints	"It's expensive and time-consuming to attend PD sessions that are far from our area."	- Financial and time burden for teachers	- Offer more local PD options - Implement virtual training sessions

Transportation and accessibility issues pose substantial barriers to professional development (PD) for Madrasah teachers in Bukidnon. Many educators face high costs and significant time commitments associated with traveling to PD sessions, which are often held in distant locations. These logistical challenges can be prohibitive, making it difficult for teachers to participate fully in opportunities that are essential for their professional growth. The long distances and associated expenses not only limit attendance but also contribute to teacher fatigue and stress, which can negatively impact their effectiveness in the classroom (Karmila & Wijaya, 2020).

To overcome these barriers, it is crucial to decentralize PD sessions and offer more local or virtual options. By bringing professional development closer to the communities where teachers live and work, educational authorities can significantly enhance accessibility. Localized PD sessions can reduce travel time and costs, allowing educators to engage in meaningful learning experiences without the added pressure of long commutes (Edutopia, 2021). Additionally, virtual options can provide flexibility, enabling teachers to participate in training at their convenience, thus accommodating their busy schedules and personal responsibilities (PowerSchool, n.d.).

Implementing these strategies not only benefits teachers but also ultimately enhances the educational experience for their students. When educators have access to relevant and timely professional development opportunities, they are better equipped to implement effective teaching practices that foster student engagement and learning outcomes. Therefore, addressing transportation and accessibility challenges is essential for creating a supportive environment that promotes continuous professional growth among Madrasah teachers in Bukidnon.

Conclusions

This study highlights the critical professional development needs of Madrasah teachers in rural Bukidnon, emphasizing the necessity of targeted training and support mechanisms that address the unique challenges faced by these educators. The findings reveal a pressing demand for technology integration and subject-specific training in Islamic Studies, both of which are crucial to the effectiveness of Madrasah teachers in an evolving educational landscape. Without access to these resources, educators in the Madrasah system may struggle to keep pace with both pedagogical best practices and advancements in educational technology, ultimately affecting the quality of learning for their students.

Barriers such as geographic isolation, poor internet connectivity, and financial constraints significantly hinder teachers' access to professional development opportunities. These challenges not only limit participation in external training but also widen the gap between rural and urban educators, leaving rural Madrasah teachers at a disadvantage. Additionally, the lack of administrative support and structured professional development programs exacerbates the problem, making it difficult for teachers to engage in continuous professional growth.

However, the research also suggests potential solutions to overcome these barriers. The call for localized training and blended learning approaches presents a practical and flexible way to deliver professional development, allowing teachers to access relevant, context-specific training without the burden of long-distance travel. Moreover, the establishment of professional learning communities (PLCs) and peer mentoring networks can provide ongoing support and collaboration, enabling teachers to share resources and strategies even in resource-constrained environments.

In conclusion, addressing the professional development needs of Madrasah teachers in rural Bukidnon requires a collaborative and strategic effort from both local and national educational authorities. By prioritizing localized and accessible training programs, alongside fostering a culture of peer support, the gap in professional development opportunities can be bridged. This, in turn, will empower Madrasah teachers to deliver a higher quality of education, ensuring that learners in rural areas receive the educational experiences they deserve.

To enhance the professional development (PD) of Madrasah teachers in rural Bukidnon, several targeted recommendations can be made. First, addressing personal and family challenges is crucial. Implementing flexible PD schedules that accommodate teachers' family responsibilities can help alleviate the time constraints they face. Additionally, offering PD opportunities through local or online formats can reduce the burden of travel and make professional development more accessible. These adjustments will enable teachers to balance their professional and personal lives more effectively, ensuring they can participate in and benefit from PD programs.

Second, improving the educational environment is essential for supporting both teaching and professional development. Investing in updated teaching materials and enhancing school facilities will provide teachers with the resources they need to deliver high-quality instruction and engage in PD. Equipping Madrasahs with modern educational resources and infrastructure will not only improve the overall teaching environment but also facilitate more effective professional growth. Ensuring that PD programs include training on new resources and teaching methods will further support teachers in adapting to evolving educational standards.

Lastly, addressing community and social influences, health and well-being concerns, and transportation and accessibility issues is vital for a comprehensive approach to professional development. Incorporating cultural values into PD programs and involving community leaders can help align new teaching practices with local expectations. Implementing wellness programs and providing support for travel costs or virtual PD options will mitigate stress and accessibility barriers. By taking these steps, the educational experience for both teachers and learners in Bukidnon can be significantly improved, fostering a more supportive and effective learning environment.

References

- Creative Educator. (2019). Operationalizing flexible professional learning. Retrieved from <https://creativeeducator.tech4learning.com/2019/articles/operationalizing-flexible-professional-learning>
- Department of Education (DepEd). (2016). DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2016: National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers. Retrieved from DepEd website
- Department of Education (DepEd). (2019). DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2019: Guidelines on the Implementation of the Madrasah Education Program. Retrieved from DepEd website
- Edutopia. (2021). Flexible professional development. Retrieved from <https://www.edutopia.org/article/flexible-professional-development>
- Gonzales, A. (2015). The Impact of Professional Development on Teachers' Instructional Practices in the Philippines: A Case Study. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(17), 56-63.
- Karmila, K., & Wijaya, A. (2020). Striking a balance between centralized and decentralized decision making: A school-based management practice for optimum performance. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Economic Review*, 3(4), 10-17. <https://doi.org/10.36923/ijsser.V3i4.122>
- Khan, A. (2018). Challenges in the Professional Development of Islamic School Teachers: A Comparative Study. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 32(6), 1004-1021.
- Liu, J., & Meyer, L. (2019). Teacher Professional Development and Student Outcomes: An Overview of Research. *Educational Review*, 71(2), 239-260.
- Mendoza, L. (2021). Addressing the Needs of Rural Educators: Strategies for Effective Professional Development. *Philippine Journal of Education*, 98(2), 45-58.
- Mizell, H. (2010). Why professional development matters. *Educational Leadership*, 68(5), 80-82.
- NASPA. (2023). Cultivating a culture of professional development. Retrieved from <https://www.naspa.org/blog/cultivating-a-culture-of-professional-development>
- PIDS. (2011). Mobilizing LGU Support for Basic Education: Focus on the Special Education Fund. Philippine Institute for Development Studies.
- PowerSchool. (n.d.). Professional development for teachers. Retrieved from <https://www.powerschool.com/blog/the-three-most-common-types-of-teacher-professional-development-and-how-to-make-them-better/>
- ReachOut Schools. (n.d.). Teacher wellbeing - ReachOut Schools. Retrieved from <https://schools.au.reachout.com/teacher-wellbeing>

UNESCO. (2015). *Philippine Education For All 2015: Implementation and Challenges*.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Rolly S. Ortiz Jr.

Northern Mindanao Division of Bukidnon
Department of Education – Philippines